

All Patient Cases (images and clinical data) collected until 23/04/2024 in the CHAIMELEON Repository related to Breast cancer.

ID: 630ee013-a7b8-4e01-823b-81918543d3f6

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/630ee013-a7b8-4e01-823b-81918543d3f6/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 1507

Subjects count: 1238

Age range: Between 27 years and 97 years

Sex: Female, Male, Unkown

Body part(s): BREAST, HEAD, ABDOMEN, CHEST, MAMOGRAFIA, Unknown

Modality: MG, MR, CT, CR, Unknown